

Appendix Table 1: NACE Codes Used for Orbis Firm Selection
 Accompanies Ch. 12 Making the future of the city: insights and lessons from Athens and Rotterdam
 Authors: Younghyun Kim, Amanda Brandellero, and Karel Van den Berghe

NACE Code	Description	Group	Category (Sub-sector of Creative Economy)	Source
13.10	Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.20	Weaving of textiles	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.30	Finishing of textiles	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.91	Manufacture of knitted and crocheted fabrics	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.93	Manufacture of carpets and rugs	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.96	Manufacture of technical and industrial textiles	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
13.99	Manufacture of other textiles n.e.c.	Textile production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.11	Manufacture of leather clothes	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.12	Manufacture of work wear	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)

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14.13	Manufacture of other outerwear	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.14	Manufacture of underwear	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.19	Manufacture of babies' garments and sports clothing and clothing accessories	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.20	Manufacture of articles of fur	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.31	Manufacture of knitted and crocheted hosiery	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
14.39	Manufacture of knitted and crocheted apparel	Apparel production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
15.11	Tanning and dressing of leather; dressing and dyeing of fur	Footwear and leather goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
15.12	Manufacture of luggage, handbags and the like, saddlery and harness	Footwear and leather goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
15.20	Manufacture of footwear	Footwear and leather goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
17.23	Manufacture of paper stationary	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)

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18.11	Printing of newspapers	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
18.12	Other printing	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
18.13	Pre-press and pre-media services	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
18.14	Binding and related services	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
18.20	Reproduction of recorded media	Printing and media reproduction	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
23.11	Manufacture of flat glass	Glass and ceramics production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
23.12	Shaping and processing of flat glass	Glass and ceramics production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
23.13	Manufacture of hollow glass	Glass and ceramics production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)

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23.14	Manufacture of glass fibres	Glass and ceramics production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
23.41	Manufacture of ceramic household and ornamental articles	Glass and ceramics production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
31.01	Interior construction and manufacture of business furniture	Furniture and interior goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
31.02	Manufacture of kitchen furniture	Furniture and interior goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
31.09	Manufacture of other furniture	Furniture and interior goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
32.12	Manufacture of jewellery and related articles	Lifestyle and recreational goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
32.20	Manufacture of musical instruments	Lifestyle and recreational goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Eurostat (2018), Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
32.30	Manufacture of sports goods	Lifestyle and recreational goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)
32.40	Manufacture of games and toys	Lifestyle and recreational goods production	Cultural manufacturing	Grodach & Guerra-Tão (2024)

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58.11	Book publishing	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
58.13	Publishing of newspapers	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
58.21	Publishing of computer games	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
59.11	Motion picture, video and television programme production activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
59.12	Motion picture, video and television programme post-production activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
59.13	Motion picture, video and television programme distribution activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
59.14	Motion picture projection activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
59.20	Sound recording and music publishing activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
60.10	Radio broadcasting	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)

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60.20	Television programming and broadcasting activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
63.91	News agency activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
74.20	Photographic activities	Media and Entertainment	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
61.10	Wired telecommunications activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
61.20	Wireless telecommunications activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
61.30	Satellite telecommunications activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
61.90	Other telecommunications activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
62.01	Writing, producing, and publishing of software	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
62.02	Computer consultancy and support	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
62.03	Computer facilities management	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
62.09	Other information technology and computer service activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
63.11	Data processing, hosting, and related activities	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)
63.12	Web portals	ICT	Rutten et al. (2023)

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71.11	Architectural activities	Creative business services	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
73.11	Advertising agencies	Creative business services	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
74.10	Specialised design activities	Creative business services	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
74.30	Translation and interpretation activities	Creative business services	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
85.52	Cultural education	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018)
90.01	Performing arts	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
90.02	Support activities to performing arts	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
90.03	Artistic creation	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
90.04	Operation of arts facilities	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
91.01	Library and archives activities	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
91.02	Museums activities	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)

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91.03	Operation of historical sites and buildings and similar visitor attractions	Arts and cultural heritage	Eurostat (2018), Rutten et al. (2023)
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